

Spatial modelling of the relationship between the urban form and population data

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Summary

This study examines methods for modelling relationships between urban form patterns and socio-demographic characteristics using spatially explicit architecture. By comparing linear and nonlinear dimensionality reduction techniques alongside geographically weighted prediction models, we analyse the interplay between population and morphological patterns in Czechia. The study combines a morphometric classification of over 4 million buildings with detailed 2021 Census data at the basic settlement unit level. This methodological framework evaluates the effectiveness of various modelling approaches contributing to our understanding of the relationship between people and their built environment.

KEYWORDS: urban form, geodemographics, spatial modelling, geographically weighted models

1 Introduction

The quantification of an interplay between two aspects of cities—their population and their urban form—is critical to understanding the relationships between who people are and where they live, either by choice or not. Using spatially explicit architecture, this paper provides new insight into the methods of modelling the relationship between sociodemographic factors and urban form. The socio-demographic variables provide quantitative insight into society’s structure, while the morphological analysis quantifies the physical environment. This combination allows for quantitative analysis of the relationship between people and places, leading to the assessment of (in)equality of access to the desired place to live and the capability of different groups to make such a choice. However, the methods of such an analysis are not very well mapped in the existing literature.

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2 Background

Neighborhood-level classifications of physical aspects of cities belong primarily to the field of urban morphology, an area of research spreading between urban geography and architecture (Moudon, 1997), focusing on the study of the patterns of urban form composed of configurations of streets, the dimensions and spatial distribution of buildings and related urban elements. While originating from the primarily qualitative methods, urban morphology has entered the era of data science with the developments of urban morphometrics - a set of methods aimed at characterizing urban form based on its measurable traits (Dibble et al., 2019). Starting from the scale of neighborhoods, these methods evolved into scalable analytics that characterize whole countries while retaining the granularity of individual features (Araldi & Fusco, 2024; Fleischmann et al., 2022).

Where urban morphology deals with the physical structure of cities, socio-demographic indicators cover the population. If linked to a particular neighborhood, these indicators are valuable for understanding the complex relationships between people and places.

Both socio-demographic characteristics and urban morphology reflect a single aspect of urban life. However, it is not that common for these two to be considered in tandem, trying to understand the links between people and built form. The research direction that can capture both socio-demographic nuances in the population and urban morphology in its complexity requires a multi-disciplinary approach that started to appear only recently, as shown in the works of Venerandi et al. (2018) and Venerandi et al. (2024) quantifying the relationship between a small subset of morphological variables and socio-economic indices, Sapena et al. (2021) linking quality of life to morphology (albeit using a simplified typology of Local Climate Zones (Stewart & Oke, 2012)), Oliveira (2024) examining the correlation between urban form and socioeconomic and environmental diversity, or Duque et al. (2015) capturing morphology through remotely sensed landscape metrics. Polishchuk et al. (2024) hypothesizes that regression analysis could be applied in planning research to assess the impact of urban form on socioeconomic variables. However, neither combines the recent advantages in urban morphometrics with those in social geography, leaving the relationship between urban form patterns and the population inhabiting largely unmapped territory.

3 Methods and data

This study compares different methods for assessing the relationship between urban form and population characteristics using predictive modelling. It first examines linear and nonlinear dimensionality reduction techniques for census variables to avoid the curse of dimensionality induced by a large number of variables in the census data. Second, it explores the nature of the classification task by comparing binary geographically weighted linear and nonlinear prediction models compared to baseline global models.

In order to perform this analysis, the project uses the existing morphometric classification of urban structure released by Fleischmann and Samardzhiev (2025), covering over 4 million buildings in Czechia. The classification is available in the form of a hierarchical taxonomy reflecting the morphological (dis)similarity and, in fact, the historical and socio-economic origins of the different development patterns. This is complemented by the detailed population data provided by the Czech

Census of 2021, which allows us to infer relationships between the built environment and the sociodemographic characteristics of the Czech population at the granular scale of the basic settlement unit (adequate to the English Output Areas).

4 Results

The results indicate that the choice of dimensionality reduction technique and machine learning model impacts the performance of predicting relationships between urban form and population data. Factor analysis (FA) and Principal Component Analysis (PCA), representing linear dimensionality reduction techniques, combined with both models generally perform well across most urban type developments. Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP), while effective in some cases, shows slightly lower performance compared to FA and PCA.

Logistic Regression (LR) models tend to underperform compared to Random Forest (RF) in categories like Street-aligned Development and Dense Urban Development which implicates non-linear relationship between people and these development types.

Table 1: Preliminary results of Macro F1-score of different dimensionality reduction techniques and machine learning models across different development types

Dimension. reduction	Model	Central Urban	Dense Urban	Large Scale	Linear Road Network	Sparse Road Network	Sparse Rural	Street- aligned
FA	LR	0.618	0.567	0.746	0.304	0.686	0.593	0.481
	RF	0.638	0.622	0.755	0.478	0.695	0.562	0.515
PCA	LR	0.642	0.553	0.756	0.257	0.709	0.578	0.478
	RF	0.634	0.638	0.774	0.478	0.694	0.556	0.512
UMAP	LR	0.624	0.613	0.755	0.309	0.701	0.572	0.498
	RF	0.603	0.584	0.75	0.441	0.651	0.508	0.474

5 Conclusions

The outcomes provide an evaluation of methods for modelling the relationship between socio-demographic factors and urban form by combining traditional machine learning methods with spatial analysis techniques. Each of the tested approaches is valid on its own. However, as their performance and ability to adapt to the geographic variations differ, the recommendations formulated by this research inform future work in the context of people-places relationship assessments. Furthermore, the paper highlights the potential use of spatially explicit analysis in urban planning for uncovering complex relationships. At the same time, the case study of Czechia offers new insights into the interplay between socio-demographic characteristics and urban morphology in the Country, shedding light on how social and demographic structures link to the built environment at fine spatial scales. This approach not only deepens the understanding of these dynamics but also opens up opportunities for further exploration.

5.1 Code and data availability

The reproducible code used in the paper is available in the public repository at https://github.com/uscuni/people_places

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